

AIRCRAFT BATTLE VISUALIZATION BASED ON MIXED-REALITY

Vitradisa Pratama (Mayasari Bakti University), Ary Setijadi Prihatmanto (Bandung Institute of Technology), Agus Sukoco (Bandar Lampung University), Dr. Rahadian Yusuf (Bandung Institute of Technology), Dr. Reza Darmakusuma (Bandung Institute of Technology), Dr. Agus Budiyo (Bandung Institute of Technology)

itb.ac.id@gmail.com

Abstract. In aircraft battle, an airforce pilot must continue to focus on the battlefield for assault the enemy. This condition require the pilot to access and manage battlefield information inside the airplane cockpit. The one way to access and manage battlefield information inside the cockpit seamlessly is to use head mounted display preinstalled in the pilot helmet. Inside the head-mounted display battlefield data was visualized in mixed reality platform, with this platform, the surrounding civil airplane position and enemy target is visualized with virtual object and the virtual object is merged seamlessly with real world also the plane orientation is visualized with gauge bar inside the head-mounted display. That data is visualized inside the Microsoft Hololens, a mixed-reality platform device made by Microsoft. The system is based on prototyping method by making a prototype and evaluate 6 times. On the sixth prototype, application performance has increased. memory consuming Decreasaed from 238 Megabytes to 47 megabytes.

To presenting the information from which is merged seamlessly with the real world, projection of airplane position and target position must be accurate so the data and information like the position, distance and heading displayed correctly as same as in the real world. The data from server is projecting using Mercator Projection inside the Hololens spatial world is required for accurate information and following the mission for succesfull the assault mission. On the synthetic testing, data is tested using data input coordinates 0.0 to 0.1 and successfully projected onto mercator to 0, 111.31949079237 which once compared with the input of the haversine formula then the distance between the two coordinates is 111,31949079237 meters. The results of the aircraft and target visualization is clearly visible as long as the distance is still under 20 meters and the green color is the most visible color to use as the display color of the interface. Comparison of intensity saturation in the color of the background user interface and a minimum of 30 and a comparison of the intensity value color user interface and background at least 20 notes with the color of the user interface is more dominant than the background.

Keywords: *head mounted display, mixed- reality, mercator, airplane battlefield, visualization.*

1. Introduction

In aircraft battles with the fighters of the air force, a pilot is required to continue to focus on the battle in front of the eyes. This requires that a pilot should be able to access and manage the information battle inside the cockpit of the airplane. One way to access information and efficient aircraft instrument panel is by installing a Head Mounted Display (HMD) on the helmet used by the pilot. On the Head Mounted Display, the condition of aircraft battle is visualized with Mixed Reality technology for position visualization, distance and target enemies by displaying a virtual object which is blended with the real environment. In addition, the orientation of the aircraft visualized inside display interface on the Head Mounted Display and orientation information must be visible in any condition even when conditions are in the dark environment. The data is visualized on a Microsoft HoloLens platform, a mixed reality platform from Microsoft. Head mounted display in General show information orientation angles such as aircraft and pilots, guiding pilots in pursuit of the target and check the condition of the artillery at the planes. But other information in a more detailed scale such as the visualization of the existence of enemy planes, the distance between the pilot and the target for monitoring positions are still not integrated with head mounted display. This paper is divide by 4 section. Section 1 is introduction. Section 2 is explaining related literature, concept and technology on Head Mounted Display. Section 3 is explaining research method, design and application concept. Section 4 is display the research result.

2. Related Literture

This section is explaining about related literature, concept and technology on Head Mounted Display.

2.1. Mixed Reality

Mixed Reality is a technology that can combine the environment from the real world and the virtual world to create a new environment in which is the virtual objects can coexist and interact directly physically and digitally at the same time. Mixed reality is essentially a merger

of augmented reality and virtual reality. The process of merging the virtual world and the real world on mixed reality is quite complex because of the combination of several technologies at once, such as a three-dimensional model, tracking, computer human interface, haptic feedback, simulations, rendering and display techniques, and merged seamlessly into the real world. Mixed reality technology is itself a response to the limitations of the technology of virtual reality and augmented reality where the reality that exists in the real world not replaced entirely by virtual reality, yet integrated virtual objects completely with the real world as a whole. User interaction with a virtual object can be done directly without going through additional tools such as virtual reality and augmented reality. With mixed reality, the limit between the virtual world with the real world will be decreased.

2.2. Head Mounted Display

Head-Mounted Display is a device that its main function is to display the virtual object and this device is used by mount it at the head of its users. There are two types of Head Mounted Display (HMD) is used, i.e. an opaque HMD and see-through HMD.

2.2.1. Opaque Head Mounted Display

When used in one eye, the user must adjust the view of the real world that are observed in the eye that are not covered by the HMD with graphic imagery projected onto the both of the user's eye covered by the Head Mounted Display. However, when used with cover both of the user's eye, user can see the conditions that exist in the real world through his capture from a camera on the Head Mounted Display device.

2.2.2. See-Through Head Mounted Display

Unlike the Opaque Head Mounted Display, See-through Had Mounted Display absorb light from the surrounding environment, this allowing the user to directly observe the real world with the eyes. In addition, a mirror like system is placed in front of the eye which reflects light for the uses of computer-generated graphics.

2.3. Coordinate References System

The coordinate reference system is a system that is used for the definition of a coordinate or some point in space. The reference system is used as a reference to determine the value of a point. This is a reference system commonly used to describe the position:

1. CIS (Conventional Inertial System)

Conventional Inertial System is a coordinate reference system used for describing the position and movement of the satellite. The nature of this system is geocentric and referred based on the sky.

2. CTS (Conventional Terrestrial System)

Conventional Terrestrial System is the coordinate reference system is used to declare a position on the Earth's surface. The nature of this system is geocentric and referred based on the earth.

One of the implementations of the CTS is WGS 84 (World Geodetic System 1984), WGS 84 is a system that is currently used by the GPS navigation system. The WGS 84 coordinate system is basically a CTS defined, realized and monitored by NIMA (National Imagery and Mapping) United States.

2.4. Mercator Projection

Mercator projection is a cylindrical map projection popularized in 1569 by Flemish Gerardus Mercator. Mercator projection is a projection map are commonly used on the cruise. This projection depicting the Earth on the cylinder axis fields connecting Earth with balls, then as if the cylinders are opened into flat areas. This projection has the characteristic that is has a small distortion in the Equatorial area but an increasingly large if the distortion towards the polar regions.

2.5. Haversine Formula

The concept of projection inside the Microsoft HoloLens is every single unit vector either x axis, y axis and z axis is represented as a meter meaning one unit of distance in the HoloLens equals one meter in the real world. Therefore if wished to measure the distance between two points of

latitude and longitude coordinates, we can use the Haversine Formula formulas that can be seen on

$$a = \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) + \cos\varphi_1 \cdot \cos\varphi_2 \cdot \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$c = 2 \cdot \operatorname{atan2}\left(\sqrt{a}, \sqrt{1-a}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$d = R \cdot c \quad (3)$$

In this formula, φ is the latitude, λ is the longitude, R is the radius of the curvature of the Earth. For the near pole area, earth radius is 6,378,137 Km, for the near of equator area, earth radius is 6,356,752 Km. It should be noted that angle is using radian.

2.6. RGB and HSV colorspace

The principle of the RGB color space is like a cube that contains a combination of color value red, green and blue, while the HSV color space is more like a cylinder in a combination of colors, value based on hue, saturation and value.

Figure 1 - RGB and HSV colorspace¹

RGB color combinations derived from the combined value of red, green and blue so get a new color combination. While HSV using hue, saturation and value to specify the desired color combination. Hue is the value of the attribute that corresponds to the area that appears to be similar to one of the colors produced by RGB, could the combination of red and green, or red and blue. Saturation is the composition of the brightness of the color, and the value is the brightness of colors against a white color.

¹ Source: <https://koenig-media.raywenderlich.com/uploads/2014/03/rgbvshsv.jpg>

3. Research Method

This section will explain the method used in this research, what system architecture will be used in the making of this. How to visualize, the design of the user interface and design visualization object that will be used.

3.1. The method of Prototyping

The system is designed based on the basis of the prototyping method where before reaching the final step, the system was developed from various previous prototype. Stages of prototyping development as it follows:

1. Requirement collecting.
2. Build a prototype.
3. Evaluation of the prototype.
4. Encode system.
5. Test the system.
6. Evaluation of the system.
7. Using the system.

In stage 1, customers and developers in the same shared system defines the format and overall device needs and outline a system that will be created. On the stage 2 will be built by creating a temporary design prototype that aims to present the interim system in outline to customers such as creating examples for representation input and output. At stage 3 will be done evaluation against a prototype already built. If it fits then it will proceed to stage 4. If it is still unresolved then stage 1 to stage 3 will be repeated again until the prototype suit. At stage 4, the prototype is in compliance and agreed to be built its system with the device and the appropriate programming language. Once the prototype is complete then on stage 5 prototypes will be tested for later evaluated at stage 6. Stage 6 test whether the prototype is already appropriate and feasible to use. If not then the stage 4 and 5 do back. After 6 stages done it already can be used.

3.2. System Requirement

Based on the formulation of the problem, purpose and limitations of the problem that has been noted in before, then the system must be able to meet the following criteria:

1. Visualize Information the existence of enemy planes on the HMD.
2. Integrate information such as distance pilots and targets for monitoring positions at HMD.
3. create a mechanism for sending data from a server towards the HMD device.

To be able to meet the criteria then the system specifications must be constructed like this:

1. The server computer to send data battle
2. Head Mounted Display Device for displaying information and interaction of the pilot.
3. GPS as a reference location
4. Dummy Data as data battle

3.3. System Architecture

The overall system consists of three modules, namely Server, Messaging Service and Module HMD. Module Server as a data source from the position of the enemy and targets. Messaging Service is a module that regulates communications traffic data, this module use RabbitMQ as a service for traffic management data. HMD display module is the module which is affixed on the head/helmet pilot pilots get information to help the position of enemy planes, the orientation of the target and lock at the time of the battle. On the module of data obtained from the HMD orientation sensor which is integrated with hololens and the data processed with IMU integrated with hololens. Besides the voice input using the Cortana is already integrated in the overall system architecture of hololens is as follows..

Figure 2. Overall System Architecture

4. Design

In this section will be explained about the design for the user interface, visualization design of the existence of the aircraft and the target.

4.1. User Interface Design

The results of the readings of the sensors on the Hololens is processed to provide a user interface on the Hololens to measure and tell the pilot orientation when the battle took place. The information is visualized as the gauge bar that has a pointer needle to measure the yaw and pitch. Meanwhile, in the Middle near the crosshair (+) there are lines help to identify the orientation of the roll happens. In addition to the visualization in the form of 2D graphics, the sensor reading of the results shown in the form of numbers and can be used again to be processed further processing other than visually.

4.2. Aircraft and Target Visualization Design

The aircraft is visualized by using a simple 3D object with a model like a Airbus plane in addition to the simple object, visualized aircraft was given a description of the aircraft serial number. Information orientation of the aircraft, the position of the aircraft, serial number of the aircraft retrieved from the request data to the server.

Figure 3. User Interface and Aircraft Visualization

Visualization of the target has a concept similar to the plane visualization. Target visualized using a simple 3D object with a model of a simple cube, in addition to the Target visualized with the shape of the cube is then given a description of the type of the target and the distance between the pilot to the target. Target position information obtained from the process data requests to the server.

Figure 4. Target Visualization

5. Results

Based on concepts and designs that have been discussed before and the discussion of the results will be divided into four sub-section.

5.1. Test for Projection Accuracy

This testing is for purpose testing accuracy of mercator projection by comparing with the results of the calculations of the haversine formula. On this test will be use a starting point at coordinates 0 longitude and 0 latitude (0,0) and the end point (1,0) with a projection on WGS 84 so if plotted on Cartesian diagram, then the position and direction of movement point is (0.0) into point (1.0).

Figure 5. Position and directional movement on the test.

Note that the radius of curvature of the Earth for this testing is using the radius by 6.378,137 Km in equator because Indonesian territorial area is near the equator.

```
Longitude EPSG 4326 WGS84 gps: 1
Latitude EPSG 4326 WGS84 gps: 0
Longitude EPSG 3395 Mercator World :111.31949079327
Latitude EPSG 3395 Mercator World :0
Longitude EPSG 3857 Web Mercator :111.31949079327
Latitude EPSG 3857 Web Mercator :0
Haversine distance 0,0 WGS84 GPS to 1,0 WGS84 GPS : 111.31949079327
```

Figure 6. Projection Testing compare to the Haversine Formula

From this testing result in figure 5 we can see the the results of the mercator projection and the results of the calculation with the haversine formula is same.

5.2. User Interface Visualization Result

This test is purposed for displaying user interface and sensor reading result. The scenario is hololens is moved in different directions and rotation to test reading of sensors and data processing for information on the user interface of the Head Mounted Display. The result is done as follows.

Figure 7. Orientation Changed

In this test the orientation angle of the Head Mounted Display has changed following the readings of the sensors, pitch and yaw indicator changed on the right side and above follow the reading of the sensor output can be seen in figures 6 on the top and right near the target Crosshair. However the reading sensor constrained when it reaches the boundary of 180 or -180 degrees and then the pointer will be moved to the opposite side.

5.3. Aircraft and Target Visualization Result

In this test data is loaded from the server and GPS is converted from WGS 84 coordinate format to the units in meters using Mercator Projection. The results can be viewed as done in figure 7.

Figure 8. Aircraft Visualization

There are limitations on this projection distances that can be shown inside Hololens. If the distance from the position of the user and the target Hololens exceeds 20 meters then the object cannot be seen, this can be overcome by changing the scale settings of the virtual environment on the Hololens but if the object is too far away then the object becomes very small and cannot be seen. Need to specified limits field of view for this. This applies also to the projection and visibility of the target.

Figure 9. Target Visualization

5.4. Color comparison in User Interface

To determine what colors can be used for user interface in the application then we needs to do testing in environment in bright condition and the environment in dark condition. Testing using a few basic colors such as black, blue, cyan, gray, green, magenta, red, yellow and white as the base color on the display of the application interface.

Figure 10. User Interface color comparison in bright condition.

In Table 1 shows a comparison of the intensity of the color is based on using a HSV standard.

Table 1. Color Intensity in HSV Format

UI Color				Environment Color			Compare Result		
Color ID	Color Value (HSV)			Color Value (HSV)			Color Value (HSV)		
	Hue	Saturation	Value	Hue	Saturation	Value	Hue	Saturation	Value
Color.Green	132	84	94	187	13	71	-55	71	23
Color.Cyan	180	85	92	187	13	71	-7	72	21
Color.Magenta	297	75	96	187	13	71	110	62	25
Color.Blue	235	77	89	187	13	71	48	64	18
Color.Red	0	72	94	187	13	71	-187	59	23
Color.White	50	2	97	187	13	71	-137	-11	26
Color.Gray	204	20	56	187	13	71	17	7	-15

In this test, we use simulation by using digital image shown in monitor as a view for Head Mounted Display. We can see in figure 9 that the color Cyan and Green is the most excellent visibility for use as the User

Interface on the Head Mounted Display. The result is similar in the dark condition using a simulation using the emulator.

Figure 11. User Interface color comparison in dark condition.

In Table 2 shows a comparison of the intensity of the color is based on using a HSV standard.

Table 2. Color Intensity in HSV Format

UI Color			Environment Color			Compare Result			
Color ID	Color Value (HSV)			Color Value (HSV)			Color Value (HSV)		
	Hue	Saturation	Value	Hue	Saturation	Value	Hue	Saturation	Value
Color.Green	132	84	94	0	0	0	132	84	94
Color.Cyan	180	85	92	0	0	0	180	85	92
Color.Magenta	297	75	96	0	0	0	297	75	96
Color.Blue	235	77	89	0	0	0	235	77	89
Color.Red	0	72	94	0	0	0	0	72	94
Color.White	50	2	97	0	0	0	50	2	97

Color.Gray	204	20	56	0	0	0	204	20	56
------------	-----	----	----	---	---	---	-----	----	----

6. References

- [1] Abidin, H.Z., 2001, Geodesi Satelit. Jakarta : PT. Pradnya Paramitha.
- [2] Abidin, H.Z., 2007, Penentuan Posisi dengan GPS dan Aplikasinya. Jakarta : PT Pradnya Paramita.
- [3] Abidin, H.Z., A.Jones, J.Kahar. 2002. Survei dengan GPS. Jakarta : PT Pradnya Paramita.
- [4] Prijatna, K. 2005. *Proyeksi Peta - Hand out Kuliah*. Bandung: Fakultas Teknik Geodesi ITB.
- [5] Prihandito, A. 1998. *Proyeksi Peta*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Kanisius.
- [6] J. O'Brien, Introduction to information systems. Burr Ridge, Ill.: Irwin, 1994.
- [6] K. Curtin, "Mixed Reality will be most important tech of 2017", The Next Web. <https://thenextweb.com/insider/2017/01/07/mixed-reality-will-be-most-important-tech-of-2017/>. (12 May 2017).
- [7] "Microsoft HoloLens", Microsoft HoloLens. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/hololens>. (12 May 2017).
- [8] "Microsoft HoloLens, Why Hololens?". Microsoft HoloLens. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/hololens/why-hololens>. (12 May 2017).
- [9] "WGS 84: EPSG Projection -- Spatial Reference", Spatialreference.org. <http://spatialreference.org/ref/epsg/wgs-84/>.(12 May 2017).
- [10] "WGS 84 / World Mercator: EPSG Projection -- Spatial Reference", Spatialreference.org. <http://spatialreference.org/ref/epsg/wgs-84-world-mercator/>. (12 May 2017).
- [11] "Mercator's Projection", Math.ubc.ca, 2017. <http://www.math.ubc.ca/~israel/m103/mercator/mercator.html>. (12 May 2017).
- [12] D. R. Williams, "Earth Fact Sheet", Nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/earthfact.html>. (3 August 2017).
- [13] VOCAL Technologies, L. (2018). RGB and HSV/HSI/HSL Color Space Conversion. Vocal.com. <https://www.vocal.com/video/rgb-and-hsvhsi-hsl-color-space-conversion/> (18 January 2018).